

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL CAPITAL IN MODERN BUSINESS INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays the role and importance of social capital is increasing significantly in business activity. Social capital manifests itself in mutual trust, shared norms, values, and networking. Initially, the theory of social capital developed in relation to society, but gradually developed and moved to the company level. At the national level, social capital leads to mutually beneficial interactions between countries and nations and helps solve global problems (global warming, the threat of nuclear war, famine, etc.); at the state level, it helps strengthen democratic institutions; at the enterprise level, it helps develop trust between colleagues; at the individual level, it strengthens a person's psychological health (removes feelings of loneliness, increases self-esteem and life satisfaction). The article highlights and substantiates the key role of social capital in the formation of economic entities regarding the development and implementation of innovations.

Keywords: social capital, innovative economy, business development.

Introduction

Social capital in business is about connections between people at work. It's the trust, knowledge, and cooperation that emerge from these relationships.

The intellectualization of the modern world draws attention to the problem of social capital as a resource necessary to improve the quality of life of an individual, the formation of a knowledge economy and innovative development of the country. The fact that social connections, interaction and trust, which form the basis of social capital, influence the formation, development and accumulation of intellectual capital, which is of paramount importance and is included in the circle of the main interests of the world scientific community, is increasingly recognized.

Innovation creation is a complex process involving many different social and economic factors, as well as a wide range of individuals, institutions and firms engaged in the creation, development and dissemination of new knowledge and technologies. The era of lone inventors has passed. In modern conditions, no innovator acts alone. The innovative ability and receptivity of society are determined by the quality of the interrelations between economic agents. To effectively implement innovative activities, economic agents must have a reserve of social capital in the form of the necessary connections. Since the connections are not based on market interactions and not on a hierarchical principle, they form networks. The network organization is recognized as the most effective organizational structure for implementing innovative activities. The concept of social capital originated within the sociological scientific school and is associated with the names of P. Bourdieu and J. Coleman. J. Coleman defined social capital as the ability of subjects to benefit from participation in social networks and other social structures [5]. Currently, economists are showing significant interest in this subject of research. The influence of social capital on innovation was studied by H. Westlund, W. Chow, F. Sabatini, Sh. Gu, B.-A. Lundvall, L. Myasnikova, A. Zuev.

Social capital includes not hierarchical or commodity-money, but network relations of individuals. Unlike hierarchical relations, social capital presupposes voluntary interaction of equal subjects. Unlike market

relations, as a result of this interaction, an exchange of values of an emotional, material or informational nature occurs on a non-commercial basis.

Hierarchical structures have limited learning capacity, and market structures do not facilitate the establishment of trust relationships. Thus, in a knowledge-based economy, the role and importance of social capital increases.

Like any type of capital, social capital has an incorporated state (in the form of reproducible dispositions and demonstrated abilities), an objectified (material) state, and an institutionalized (formalized) state.[4]. Social capital in its objectified state represents network (horizontal) connections. In its institutionalized state, it represents the reputation and image of economic agents.

The theory of industrial districts, clusters, the theory of national and regional innovation systems and the concept of the "triple helix" note the importance of social interactions of economic agents in the creation of innovations.

By developing and using social networks, the organization develops the ability to absorb knowledge, which allows it to quickly obtain new knowledge from universities and other research institutes. Innovative companies with high knowledge absorption ability are able to quickly develop innovative products.

Open Innovation and Social capital

Consideration of innovation processes that occur within the organization and their dependence on social capital would not be complete without taking into account inter-organizational interactions. The literature studying innovation has long focused on how individual innovators and teams organize their work to invent and introduce new ideas and products into the production process. However, starting with the pioneering works of S. Freeman and V. Lundvall, the term "national innovation system" came into scientific use, where the innovation is presented as a continuous process that encompasses stages starting from the birth of an innovative idea to the diffusion, absorption and use of innovative products (Freeman, 1987, Freeman, 1995, Lundvall, 1985, Lundvall, 1992). At the same time, emphasis should be placed on the importance of interactive learning for innovation, which takes place

both in the production process and during the sale of goods and after-sales service to consumers.

A little later, E. von Hippel demonstrated that innovations occur at any stage of economic activity and in various sectors of the economy. Accordingly, producers, suppliers, end users, and even competitors can serve as sources of innovation (Hippel, 1988). The importance of the interaction of various economic agents and organizations in the innovation process was emphasized in the works, in particular, (Brown and Eisenhardt, 1995), (Szulanski, 1996), (Baum, Calabrese, and Silverman, 2000) and others, which served as the theoretical basis for the birth of the concept of open innovation (Chesbrough, 2006), affirming the “interactionist” view of the innovation process.

The model of open innovation assumes that a certain organization uses knowledge from various sources to increase its innovative activity and in this way obtains additional value for customers (Maltsev, Sala, and Buketov, 2022). In other words, the firm does not seek to generate innovations completely independently, but tries to use internal and external ideas in an optimal way in order to be more effective in managing costs and risks, to accelerate the development of technologies.

The sources of knowledge, as a rule, are suppliers, research centers, universities, customers, competitors, companies with additional knowledge offers, which are united in a network of dense interaction which takes various organizational forms, including alliances, clusters, and joint projects. It is quite clear that interaction within such organizational structures requires integration and coordination, which, in turn, creates the need to create units with appropriate functions and, as a result, attract additional resources which can be significantly lower under conditions of relative commonality of socio-cultural values of the participants of interactions and their willingness to cooperate. This actualizes the importance of social capital to ensure coordination effect.

As practice shows, the previous interaction of representatives of various organizations, which were built in the field of close scientific contacts and exchange of professional experience, formed a circle of people with similar values and served as a basis for agreeing actions already within the newly created cooperation structures. Specialists who received education at the same universities, but worked in different companies, had more chances to build more effective cooperation in the field of innovation than representatives of other educational systems.

Transaction costs are important for the effectiveness of the open innovation model, including the costs of conducting negotiations and concluding agreements with participants in the innovation process, resolving interfirm conflicts (Slowinski and Sagal, 2010), monitoring information provided by partners (Maskell, 2000).

Social capital reduces these transaction costs by establishing relationships based on trust. When counterparties trust each other, the creation of alliances, clusters, etc. does not require lengthy negotiations, and agreements are mostly concluded in the form of implicit contracts. A high level of social capital makes the situation for partners more transparent and predictable,

which does not require additional costs for checking the authenticity of counterparties' statements. All this significantly saves the resources of the group, which can be directed to innovations.

This process is facilitated by the Internet and other means of communication, which simplify access to information, save time for searching for partners, and facilitate interaction that would be very expensive at a distance. This idea was developed by J. Baum, T. Calabrese, B. Silverman, demonstrating the effectiveness of Canadian biotech start-ups depending on the creation of alliances and their integration into a network that provided access to a variety of information. S. Ouechtati, K. K. Masmoudi, C. Slim established the relationship between social capital and open innovation, on the one hand, and the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises in Tunisia (Ouechtati, Masmoudi and Slim, 2022). In turn, S. Scott, M. Hughes and P Hughes found that informal connections between participants in the innovation process almost double the size of the network and provide access to resources.

Therefore, innovations are not created in a vacuum, but are the result of the interaction of many participants united in sustainable networks which contribute to innovation by reducing transaction costs, overcoming cultural and cognitive distance, and promoting collective learning (Pilipenko, 2013). Accordingly, cooperation in modern conditions increasingly take on the characteristics of a network, changing the market structure and nature of competition which, in the field of innovation, takes place mainly between network associations, while vertical integration is inferior to horizontal connections.

Implementing innovative activities in companies

Self-organization, one of the principles of innovative companies, involves the rejection of total control inherent in traditional hierarchical organizations. At the same time, delegation of decision-making to the lowest possible level of the organization occurs.

Self-organization becomes possible only on the basis of trust in employees and requires maximum use of capabilities at all levels of the organization. Companies 3M, HP, Motorola have decentralized decision-making processes, delegating these powers to the level of teams and divisions, and also encourage the creation of small businesses [9]. Changing organizational structures when implementing the principle of self-organization helps to increase the openness of the company and facilitate interaction with the outside world. Traditional hierarchical structures with clear boundaries between the organization and the external environment are being replaced in Western companies by more flexible structures - networks, virtual organizations and alliances with much more permeable boundaries.

Thus, social capital plays the role of the most important resource in the process of implementing innovative activities. Its formation in the regional innovation system presupposes cooperation of enterprises with universities and other organizations, and also requires the implementation of an appropriate innovation policy. The innovation policy of the organization

should be aimed at finding and encouraging social contacts within the framework of intellectual partnership with representatives of domestic and foreign enterprises, with universities and state research institutions. At the same time, it is necessary to change organizational structures, increase the degree of their openness for interaction with the external environment, decentralize decision-making processes, delegate powers to the team level, manage the ideology and corporate culture of the organization.

Conclusion

The main advantage of Social Capital for innovation is to be its comprehensiveness, as it addresses many elements that play an important role in innovations. It not only refers to investment in social networks or relationships, but also emphasizes the necessary cognitive quality of connections and collective actions to produce new knowledge and knowledge products. It focuses on the powerful creativity of the connections and their collaboration.

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